

A study to assess decision making power regarding postnatal diet, exclusive breast feeding and family planning methods among postnatal women in selected rural communities, West Bengal

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INTRODUCTION:

Women autonomy in India is a much-debated issue. Although almost all the social scientists and researchers agree with the fact that woman in India are in a very low status in almost every region of this country but there is a debate on the extent of its impact on various socio-cultural and demographic aspects. Because of their low autonomy the women remained far behind than what they could have achieved in presence of a high autonomy. Since India has a patriarchal society; men are placed in a more advantageous position than women. The other things are the inheritance and succession practices which tend to neglect women. Also the family lineage and the living arrangements all are centred on men. Even the child rearing and caring practices also reflect the male supremacy. Access to nutrition, child care and education all favour boys over girls. From a very early age, a girl is socialized to give priority to the needs of the male members in the family. As a result of all these factors, men play a dominating role in every social aspect, keeping women with a very low autonomy and a low self-esteem. Women's empowerment is essentially an effort to rectify this imbalance and attain gender equity.

One neglected area of research is the role of traditional beliefs in postpartum practices in modern culture. The level of congruence between traditional beliefs and modern health practices is largely unknown and yet this is likely to play an important role in health and patient education.

Every year, two million Indian children died before their fifth birthday, most of them from preventable causes. Global evidence showed that in developing countries optimal breastfeeding is the most important child survival intervention and the earlier the baby is breastfed, within the first hour of birth. Globally it is recommended that infants be fed only breast milk for the first six months of life with no other foods or fluids not even water, referred to as exclusive breastfeeding.

However, in India, only 46 percent of infants were exclusively breastfed and rates have shown little improvement in the last decade. Exclusive breastfeeding had protected over 1.7 million infants against under-nutrition, disease and death in Assam alone in 2010, though India had 33rd place (IFBAN-ASIA, 2007) in regard with Exclusive Breastfeeding Practices all over the Asia. In the Initiation of breastfeeding within one hour of birth India had received 56th place and only 24.5 percent of the babies were breastfed within one hour of birth (NFHS-3). Over the last decade, overwhelming scientific evidence supporting the integral role of breastfeeding in the survival, growth and development of a child, as well as in the health and well-being of a mother, has come to light.

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), breast milk has the complete nutritional requirements that a baby needs for healthy development. Furthermore, it is safe and contains antibodies that help protect infants and boost immunity. Consequently, breastfeeding contributes to reduced infant morbidity and mortality due to diarrhoea, respiratory or ear infections and other infectious diseases. For the mother, breastfeeding is economical; breast milk is always available, clean and at the right temperature. Breastfeeding also delays the return of fertility and reduces the risk of developing breast and ovarian cancers. The WHO recommends that for the first six months of life, infants should be exclusively breastfed to achieve optimal growth, development and health. Thereafter, infants should receive nutritionally adequate and safe complementary foods, while continuing to breastfeed for up to two years or more. Globally, less than 40% of infants under six months of age are exclusively breastfed, despite the documented benefits of breastfeeding. In addition, only 46.4% of infants aged less than six months in India are exclusively breastfed. In many Indian societies, exclusive breastfeeding is influenced by various socio-economic, cultural and biological factors. The rates of exclusive breastfeeding have shown little improvement in the last decade excluding some states like Assam

where, as a result of concerted effort, in the last four years over 1.7 million Assamese infants have been exclusively breastfed, protected against under nutrition and disease, and given the best start in life.

While breastfeeding is a natural act, it is also a learned behaviour. Extensive research has confirmed that mothers require active support to begin and sustain appropriate breastfeeding practices. Studies have generally highlighted the lack of autonomy and decision making power among young mothers, as decisions on infant feeding significantly involves the decision of extended family. In India for instance, mixed feeding was found to begin within the first 48 hours after birth, as advised by paternal grandmothers, who were perceived to be key decision makers when it comes to good parenting. However, grandmothers (and fathers) are reported not to be actively involved in information, education and communication (IEC) activities on EBF that largely target mothers. Grandmothers' and fathers' lack of information on and support for EBF have been reported as a significant barrier to the continuation of breastfeeding.

Use of contraception is influenced by many processes most by the women's empowerment. Women's decision making power and their autonomy within the household is the most important factor affecting contraceptive use. Several studies have been conducted to analyses the relationship between these two indicators of women's empowerment and the use of contraception.

Women play a crucial role in the economic welfare of the family. They perform so many tasks depending upon the number of family members and socio-economic status. But women are traditionally less involved at all levels. In India educational development has been occurred rapidly but to keep pace with this development are the women really able to take their own decision? So the investigator felt the need to conduct a study on decision making power of postnatal women regarding postnatal diet, exclusive breast feeding and family planning methods.

Materials and Methods:

A descriptive study was conducted to assess the decision making power regarding postnatal diet, exclusive breast feeding and family planning methods among postnatal women who had baby of 6 months of age group in selected communities of West Bengal. 180 samples were taken from the rural communities under Kelejora B.P.H.C. A validated and reliable structured interview schedule was used to assess the decision making power of postnatal women regarding postnatal diet, exclusive breast feeding and family planning methods. The study was approved by the Institutional Review Board and Ethics Committee. Consents were taken from every participants of the study.

Data Collection:

Data was collected by the investigator herself from 1.10.2016 to 14.11.2016. Formal administrative permission was sought to conduct the study from Ethical Committee- Medical College and Hospital, Kolkata, Director of Medical Education and Joint Director of Health Services (Nursing), Chief Medical Officer of Health Asansol Health District and Block Medical officer of Health of Kelejora

B.P.H.C. Under Kelejora B.P.H.C. there was 16 sub centers. As the sampling technique was non probability purposive sampling technique, so the sub centers were visited one by one and the R.C.H registers were checked. Among 16 sub centers data was collected from 4 sub centers due to shortage of time. There were average 50 postnatal women within each sub center. The investigator got 25 working days and every day average 7 mothers were interviewed to collect data. So total 180 mothers were interviewed. Self- introduction and explanation was given regarding the purpose of the interview schedule. After that with the help of ASHA the home of the postnatal women was recognized and data was collected by door to door visiting. Explanation for interview schedule given to the women and informed consent was taken. Participants were asked to answer the interview without any hesitation. Data related to demographic variables and research variable were collected by structured interview schedule applying interviewing technique. After collecting the data investigator left the subject with thanks. Total time taken for one interview was approximate 20 minutes.

Data analysis:

Both descriptive and inferential statistics are used to summarize, organize and interpret the data. The collected data are coded and tabulated in the master sheet. The data are organized and analyzed according to the objectives of the study.

- Descriptive statistics-frequency and percentage are computed for sample characteristics.
- Inferential statistics- Chi square are computed for determining association of demographic variables and decision making power of postnatal mothers.

Results:

- Majority of postnatal women (76.1%) belong to 18-28 years of age group and 23.9% belongs to 29- 39 years of age group.
- Most of (96.1%) postnatal women were Hindu where only 2.8% was Muslim and 1.1% was Christian.
- Maximum subjects belong to joint family (57.2%) and 42.8% belong to nuclear family.

- Illiterate women were more in rural communities (33.9%), 26.1% women had primary education, 19.4% women had secondary education and 20.6% mothers educational level was H.S and above.
- Most of (98.3%) postnatal women were house wife where only 1.70% postnatal women were service holder.
- Majority of the family earned less than 10000 rupees (72%) and 28% families income was more than 10000 rupees.
- Majority of women that was 62.20% are primipara whereas only 37.8% women were multipara.
- Maximum (42.2%) postnatal women gained health related knowledge from health- personnel, 41.1% gained from others and 16.7% women gained from T.V.

➤ **Findings related to decision making power of postnatal mother regarding postnatal diet, exclusive breast feeding and family planning methods:**

- Most of postnatal women (97.8%) had strong decision making power in exclusive breast feeding whereas only 31.1% postnatal women had strong decision making power in family planning methods. In case of postnatal diet 76.1% postnatal women had strong decision making power, 14.5% women had partially strong decision making power and 9.4% postnatal women had poor decision making power regarding their diet. In Case of exclusive breast feeding only 2.2% postnatal women had poor decision making power. So in postnatal diet and exclusive breast feeding postnatal women had good decision making power but in the area of family planning methods, maximum women (53.9%) had partially strong decision making power and 15 % women had poor decision making power regarding this.
- Majority of postnatal women (59.5%) were always taking decision by self- regarding water intake.
- Majority of women (53.9%) were taking decision by self, 22.8% women took decision with others and 23.3% women were not taking any decision regarding intake of milk or milk product.
- In the area of intake of full diet and green leafy vegetables, postnatal women who were taking decision by self is three times more than women took decision with others. (Full diet: Self decision- 63.9%, combined decision- 22.2%, green leafy vegetables: Self decision: 65.6%, Combined decision: 21.1%) and only 13.9%, 13.3% mothers were not taking any decision in these areas respectively.
- In case of taking fruit/ fruit juice 52.8% postnatal mothers were always taking decision by self.
- In the area of taking extra meal 80% postnatal women were self-decision maker, only 8.9 % women were taking decision with others and 11.1% women were not taking any decision.
- Most of the postnatal women (97.8%) were taking decision by self-regarding breast-feeding.
- Majority of women were taking decision by self (79.5%), 14.4% women taking decision with others and 6.10% women were not taking any decision regarding pre- lacteal feeding.
- In the area feeding interval, almost all women that was 98.3% women were taking decision by self.
- Among all the areas in the area of night feed, the decision making power of postnatal women was high (100%).
- In case of birth spacing majority of multipara women were taking decisions with others (68.3%), 7.30% women were taking decision by self and 24.40% women did not take any decision.
- In case of birth spacing maximum primipara women were taking decisions with others (52%), 12.3% women were taking decision by self and 35.7% women did not take any decision.
- In the area of use of oral pill 33.3% women took decision by self, 31.7% mothers took decision with others and 35.5% women did not take any decisions.
- In the area use of condoms only 10% mothers could take decision by self.
- In case of Cu-T maximum (52.2%) women were not taking any decision
- In the area of planning of ligation 37.8% multipara women took decision by self, 29.3% women took decision with others and 32.9% women did not take any decisions.
- In the area of planning of ligation 37% primipara women were taking decision by self and 63% women do not take any decisions.
- In the area of planning of vasectomy 35% multipara women took decision by self, 28% women took decision with others and 37% women did not take any decision.
- In the area of planning of vasectomy 34.7% primipara women were taking decision by self and 65.3% mothers did not take any decision.

➤ **Findings related to association among decision making power of postnatal women regarding postnatal diet, exclusive breast feeding and family planning methods and demographic variables:**

- Statistically significant association was observed between decision making power of postnatal women regarding postnatal diet and religion ($\chi^2 = 12.0742$ $p < 0.05$ at $df = 4$).
- Highly statistically significant association was observed between decision making power of postnatal women regarding exclusive breast-feeding and religion ($\chi^2 = 23.28$ $p < 0.05$ at $df = 2$).

- Significant association was observed between decision making power of postnatal women regarding family planning methods and age of postnatal women ($\chi^2 = 17.77, p < 0.05$ at df 2).
- Statistically significant association was observed between decision making power of postnatal women regarding family planning methods and parity of women at 0.05 level of significance ($\chi^2 = 6.97, p < 0.05$ at df 2).

Fig 4: pie diagram showing percentage distribution of age of postnatal women in years.

The data presented in pie diagram depict that majority of postnatal women (76.1%) belong to 18-28 years of age group and 23.9% belongs to 29-39 years of age group.

Fig.5: Pie diagram showing percentage distribution of postnatal women according to religion.

Data presented in pie diagram show that study is done in a Hindu belt area in rural community because most of (96.1%) postnatal women are Hindu where only 2.8% is Muslim and very few women (1.1%) are Christian.

Fig.6: Bar diagram showing Percentage distribution of postnatal women according to type of family. Data presented in Fig.6 depict that maximum subjects belong to joint family (57.2%) and 42.8% belongs to nuclear family.

Fig.7: Bar diagram showing percentage distribution of postnatal women according to educational status. The data presented in bar diagram show that illiterate women are more in rural communities (33.9%), 26.1% women have primary education, 19.4% women have secondary education and 20.6% women's educational level is H.S and above.

Fig.8: Conical bar diagram showing percentage distribution of postnatal women according to occupation.

This conical bar diagram show that most (98.3%) of the postnatal women are homemaker where only 1.70% postnatal women are service holder.

Fig.9: Pie diagram showing percentage distribution of postnatal women according to income of family.

Data presented in pie diagram show that majority of the family (72%) earns less than 10000 rupees and 28% family's income is more than 10000 rupees.

Fig.10: Conical bar diagram showing percentage distribution of postnatal women according to parity of mother.

This conical bar diagram show that two third of women (62.20%) are primipara whereas only one third of women (37.8%) are multipara.

Fig.11: Bar diagram showing percentage distribution of postnatal women according to their gain in health related knowledge from media.

The data presented in bar diagram show that maximum (42.2%) postnatal women gain health related knowledge from health-personnel, 41.1% gain from others and 16.7% women gain from T.V.

SECTION –II

Fig.12: Multiple cylindrical bar diagram showing percentage distribution of decision making power of postnatal women regarding postnatal diet, exclusive breast feeding and family planning method.

Data presented in multiple bar diagram show that most of postnatal women (97.8%) have strong decision making power in exclusive breast feeding whereas only 31.1% postnatal women have strong decision making power in family planning methods. In case of postnatal diet 76.1% postnatal women have strong decision making power, 14.5% women have partially strong decision making power and 9.4% postnatal women have poor decision making power regarding their diet. In case of exclusive breast feeding only 2.2% postnatal women have poor decision making power. So in postnatal diet and exclusive breast feeding postnatal women have good decision making power but in the area of familyplanning methods, maximum women (53.9%) have partially strong decision making powerand 15 % women have poor decision making power regarding this.

Fig.13: Multiple Bar diagram showing percentage distribution of decision makingpower of postnatal women regarding postnatal diet.

Data presented in above diagram shows that- in the area of water intake- 59.5% postnatal women are always taking decision by self, 21.6% women are taking decision with others and 18.9% women are not taking any decision. Regarding intake of milk or milk product majority of women (53.9%) are taking decision by self, 22.8% mothers taking

decision with others and 23.3% women are not taking any decision.

In the area of intake of full diet and green leafy vegetables, postnatal women who are always taking decision by self is three times more than women taking decision with others. (Full diet: Self decision- 63.9%, combined decision- 22.2%, green leafy vegetables: Self decision: 65.6%, Combined decision: 21.1%) and only 13.9%, 13.3% women are not taking any decision in these areas respectively.

In case of taking fruit/ fruit juice 52.8% postnatal women are always taking decision by self, 21.6% women are taking decision with others and 25.6% women are not taking any decision. Among all the areas the decision making power is high (80%) in the area of taking extra meal. Here only 8.9 % women are taking decision with others and 11.1% women are not taking any decision.

Fig.14: Bar diagram showing percentage distribution of decision making power of postnatal women regarding exclusive breast feeding.

The data presented in Fig.14 showing that postnatal women have maximum decision making power in all areas of exclusive breast feeding.

97.8% postnatal women are taking decision by self regarding breast-feeding, only 1.7% women are taking decision with others and 0.5% women are not taking any decision.

Majority of women are taking decision by self (79.5%), 14.4% women taking decision with others and 6.10% women are not taking any decision regarding pre-lacteal feeding.

In the area of feeding interval, almost all women that is 98.3% women are taking decision by self and 1.70% women are taking decisions with others. Among all the areas the decision making power of postnatal women is high (100%) in the area of night feed.

Fig.15: Bar diagram showing percentage distribution of decision making power of postnatal women regarding birth spacing.

In case of birth spacing majority of multipara women (68.3%) are taking decisions with others, only 7.30% women are taking decision by self and 24.40% women do not take any decision. In case of primipara women 52% are taking decisions with others, 12.3% women are taking decision by self and 35.7% women do not take any decision regarding birth spacing.

Fig.16: Bar diagram shows percentage distribution of decision making power of postnatal women regarding family planning methods.

Data presented in above diagram show that-

In the area of use of oral pill 33.3% women taking decision by self, 31.7% women take decision with others and 35.5% women do not take any decisions.

In the area of use of condoms the decision making power of women is very low, only 10% women can take decision by self where as 46.7% women do not take any decision regarding this and 43.3% women take decision with others.

In case of Cu-T 21.7% postnatal women are taking decision by self, 26.1% women are taking decision with others and 52.2% women are not taking any decision. So it is clear that maximum women in this area has no decision making power.

Fig.17: Bar diagram showing percentage distribution of decision-making power of postnatal women regarding ligation.

Data presented in above diagram show that-

In the area of planning of ligation 37.8% multipara women taking decision by self, 29.3% women take decision with others and 32.9% women do not take any decision.

In case of primipara 37% women taking decision by self and 63% women do not take any decisions regarding planning of ligation.

Fig.18: Multiple cylindrical bar diagram showing percentage distribution of decision making power of postnatal women regarding Vasectomy.

Data presented in above diagram show that-

In the area of planning of vasectomy 35% multipara women taking decision by self, 28% women take decision with others and 37% women do not take any decision.

34.7% primipara women taking decision by self and 65.3% women do not take any decision regarding this area.

SECTION-III**Demographic variables**

Decision-making power	Decision-making power			Table value	df
	Strong	Partially strong	Poor		
Age:					
18-28 years	98	19	12	0.0364	5.991
29-39 years	39	7	5		
Religion:					
Hindu	133	22	16	12.0742*	9.488
Muslim	2	4	1		
Christian	2	0	0		
Type of family:					
Joint	71	16	13	5.3398	5.991
Nuclear	68	8	4		

At 0.05 level of significance.

Data presented in table 2 show that decision making power of postnatal women regarding postnatal diet is more strong (133) in Hindu religion than other religions (Christian-2, Muslim-2) and statistically significant association is observed between decision making power of postnatal women regarding postnatal diet and religion as evident from chi square value ($\chi^2 = 12.0742$ $p < 0.05$ at df 4). Here no association is found with age and type of family of postnatal women.

Table 3: Chi2 value showing association between decision making power regarding postnatal diet and education, family income, parity of postnatal women. n= 180

Demographic variables	Decision making power			2 Chi value	Table value	df
	Strong	Partially strong	Poor			
Education						
Illiterate	46	6	5	1.9748	12.592	6
Primary	33	8	5			
Secondary	25	6	4			
H.S. and above	33	6	3			
Family income						
<10,000	98	18	15	2.32	5.991	2
>10,000	39	8	2			
Parity						
Primipara	72	14	12	1.99	5.991	2

Multipara 65 12 5

At 0.05 level of significance.

Data presented in table 3 show that statistically significant association is not observed between decision making power of postnatal women regarding postnatal diet and education ($\chi^2 = 1.9748$ $p > 0.05$ at df 6), family income ($\chi^2 = 2.32$ $p > 0.05$ at df 2) and parity of mother ($\chi^2 = 1.99$ $p > 0.05$ at df 2) as evident from chi square value.

Table 4: Chi2 value showing association between decision making power regarding postnatal diet and media for gaining knowledge: n=180

Demographic variables	Decision making power			2 Chi value	Table value	df
	Strong	Partially strong	Poor			
T.V.	24	4	3	0.5641	9.488	4
Health personnel	58	10	8			
Others	55	12	6			

At 0.05 level of significance.

Data presented in table 4 show that statistically significant association is not observed between decision making power of postnatal women regarding postnatal diet and media for gaining health related knowledge as evident from chi square value ($\chi^2 = 0.5641$ $p > 0.05$ at df 4).

Table 5: Chi2 value showing association between decision making power regarding exclusive breast feeding and age religion and type of family: n=180

Demographic variables	Decision making power			2 Chi value	Table value	df
	Strong	Partially strong	Poor			
Age:						
18-28 years	125	4		0.505	3.841	1
29-39 years	51	0				
Religion:						
Hindu	169	2		23.28*	5.991	2
Muslim	5	2				
Christian	2	0				
Type of family:						
Joint	96	4		1.691	3.841	1
Nuclear	80	0				

At 0.05 level of significance.

Data presented in table 5 show that decision making power of postnatal women regarding exclusive breast feeding is

more strong in Hindu religion (169) than other religions (Christian- 2, muslim-5) and statistically significant association is observed between decisionmaking power of postnatal women regarding exclusive breast feeding and religion as evident from chi square value ($\chi^2 = 23.28$ $p < 0.05$ at $df = 2$). Here no association is found between decision making power of postnatal women regarding exclusive breast feeding and age of postnatal women and family type.

Table 6: Chi2 value showing association between decision making power regarding

exclusive breast feeding and educational status, family income and parity of postnatal women: n=180

Demographic variables	Decision making power			Table value	df
	Strong	Partially strong	2 Chi value		
Illiterate	56	1	0.128	7.815	3
Primary	45	1			
Secondary	34	1			
H.S. and above	41	1			
Family income					
<10000	128	3	0.01	3.841	1
>10000	48	1			
Parity					
Primipara	95	3	0.107	3.841	1
Multipara	81	1			

At 0.05 level of significance.

Data presented in table 6 show that statistically significant association is not observed between decision making power of postnatal women regarding exclusive breast feeding and education ($\chi^2 = 0.128$ $p > 0.05$ at $df = 3$), family income ($\chi^2 = 0.01$ $p > 0.05$ at $df = 1$) and parity of mother ($\chi^2 = 0.107$ $p > 0.05$ at $df = 1$) as evident from chi square value.

Table 7: Chi2 value showing association between decision making power regarding exclusive breast feeding and media for gaining knowledge: n=180

Demographic variables	Decision making power			Table value	df
	Strong	Partially strong	2 Chi value		
T.V.	29	2	3.0835	5.991	2

Health personnel	75	1
Others	72	1

At 0.05 level of significance.

Data presented in table 7 show that statistically significant association is not observed between decision making power of postnatal women regarding exclusive breast feeding and media for gaining health related knowledge as evident from chi square value ($\chi^2 = 3.0835$ $p > 0.05$ at $df = 2$).

**Table 8: Chi2 value showing association between decision making power regarding family planning methods and demographic variables:
n = 180**

Demographic variables	Decision making power			2 Chi value	Table value	df
	Strong	Partially strong	Poor			
Age:						
18-28 years	30	73	26	17.71*	5.991	2
29-39 years	26	24	1			
Religion:						
Hindu	53	94	24	8.98	9.488	4
Muslim	1	3	3			
Christian	2	0	0			
Type of family:						
Joint	29	56	15	0.50	5.991	2
Nuclear	27	41	12			

At 0.05 level of significance.

Data presented in table 8 show that decision making power of postnatal women regarding family planning methods is partially strong in 18-28 years of age group (73) than 29-39 years of age group (24) and statistically significant association is observed between decision making power of postnatal women regarding family planning methods and age of postnatal women as evident from chi square value ($\chi^2 = 17.71$ $p < 0.05$ at $df = 2$). Here no significant association is found with religion of postnatal women and family type.

**Table 9: Chi2 value showing association between decision making power regarding family planning methods and educational status, family type and parity of postnatal women:
n = 180**

Demographic variables	Decision making power			2 Chi value	Table value	df
	Strong	Partially strong	Poor			
Education:						
Illiterate	13	35	9	12.0447	12.592	6
Primary	19	24	3			
Secondary	9	15	11			
H.S. and above	15	23	4			
Family income:						
<10000	40	68	23	2.49	5.991	2
>10000	16	29	4			
Parity :						
Primipara	28	49	21	6.97*	5.991	2
Multipara	28	48	6			

At 0.05 level of significance.

Data presented in table 9 show that decision making power of postnatal women regarding family planning methods is poor in primipara women (21) than multipara women (6) and statistically significant association is observed between decision making power of postnatal women regarding family planning methods and parity of postnatal women as evident from chi square value ($\chi^2 = 6.97$ $p < 0.05$ at df 2). Here no association is found with educational status of postnatal women and family income.

**Table 10: Chi2 value showing association between decision making power regarding family planning methods and media for gaining knowledge:
n = 180**

Demographic variables	Decision making power			2 Chi value	Table value	df
	Strong	Partially strong	Poor			
T.V.	14	14	3	4.6952	9.488	4
Health personnel	19	43	14			
Others	23	40	10			

At 0.05 level of significance.

Data presented in table 10 show that statistically significant association is not observed between decision making power of postnatal women regarding family planning methods and media for gaining health related knowledge as evident from chi square value ($\chi^2 = 4.6952$ $p > 0.05$ at df 4).

Discussion in relation to other studies:

The present study findings showed most of postnatal women (97.8%) had strong decision making power in exclusive breast feeding whereas only 31.1% postnatal women had strong decision making power in family planning methods. In case of postnatal diet 76.1% postnatal women had strong decision making power, 14.5% women had partially strong decision making power and 9.4% postnatal women had poor decision making power regarding their diet. In Case of exclusive breast feeding only 2.2% postnatal women had poor decision making power. So in postnatal diet and exclusive breast feeding postnatal women had good decision making power but in the area of family planning methods, maximum women (53.9%) had partially strong decision making power and 15 % women had poor decision making power regarding this.

S.R. Patrikar, D.R. Basannar, Maj Seema Sharma conducted a cross sectional study on women empowerment and use of contraception among 385 currently married women in pune, India. The study gives the evidence that decision making power is low in the respondents with 48.2% of them having low level of power, while 27.6% have medium level and 3.6% having high level of decision making power, which is approximately similar with the findings of investigator's study.

Kulkarni, Rekhsde and Sharma conducted a study on knowledge and practice of 100 mothers about breast feeding in Indore city. The study findings showed that 98% mothers had knowledge about breast feeding. Knowledge about duration of exclusive breast feeding was 70% and 100% mother were aware of colostrum feeding. So this study is partially similar to the investigator's study.

Muzamil Jan and Shubeena conducted a study on an analysis of decision-making power among married and unmarried women in 2007. The study was conducted on 100 women in Jammu and Kashmir. Among these women, 50 were married and 50 were unmarried. The paper reveals that Women generally possess low decision making power regarding contraceptive use and are mainly dependent on masculine and/or familial decision making.

This study finding is incompatible with investigator's study findings:

Abeba Daniel Belay, Zelalem Birhanu Mengesha, Manay K.W. was conducted a cross sectional study on married women's decision making power on family planning use and associated factors among 567 married women in the child bearing age in Mizan city, South Ethiopia. The study result shows that more than two thirds of married women were found to be more autonomous to decide family planning use. So these study findings were not similar to the investigator's study findings.

Conclusion:

The magnitude of women's decision making power on postnatal diet and exclusive breast feeding is high in this study whereas the decision making power regarding family planning methods among postnatal women is very low. So there is an urgent need to promote more awareness among women about their role in contraceptive usage by giving them better education and financial security. It is equally important to educate the community on this important issue to provide more independence to women to take decision regarding care of their health, care of their babies and to control their fertility.

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